

INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY *for* EXTRACELLULAR VESICLES

ISEV2025 Annual Meeting, 23 – 27 April 2025, Vienna, Austria

This certificate acknowledges

Liudmyla Hrebenyk

Has attended the ISEV 2025 Annual Meeting,
23 – 27 April 2025 in Vienna, Austria

Eva-Maria Krämer-Albers, ISEV2025 Co-Chair

Eva Rohde, ISEV2025 Co-Chair

ISEV2025 | ANNUAL MEETING | VIENNA AUSTRIA
23 April Education Day | 24-27 April Annual Meeting